

DO I-PASS FOR FAIR?

Self assessment tool to
measure the FAIR-ness
of an organization

BEGINNER

INTERMEDIATE

ADVANCED

DOES YOUR ORGANIZATION...

1 **POLICY**
...have a FAIR research data policy?

2 **SERVICES**
...have a DCC which provides services to
allow research(ers) to comply with FAIR?

3 **SKILLS**
...acknowledge that FAIR capacity building
requires specific roles and skills?

4 **INCENTIVES**
...have incentives for FAIR data?

5 **ADOPTION**
...have adoption of FAIR?

Find the checklist here
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4080867

Landelijk Coördinatiepunt
Research Data Management
The data support collective